

TABLE—2. INTAKE OF CA+MG FROM THEIR MIXED CHLORIDE SOLUTIONS AT 20°, 30° AND 40°.

Clay Minerals	Initial Conc. mg./25 ml	Adsorption (x/m)		
		20°	30°	40°
Kaolinite	24.32	22.59	22.62	22.60
	22.16	11.26	11.23	11.33
	6.08	5.61	5.59	5.60
	3.04	2.82	2.80	3.04
	1.52	1.41	1.42	1.50
Illite	24.22	22.63	22.61	22.59
	12.16	11.28	12.09	11.22
	6.08	5.63	5.59	5.57
	3.04	2.81	2.82	2.81
	1.52	1.30	1.40	1.40
Bentonite	24.32	27.77	22.81	23.69
	12.16	11.34	11.31	11.28
	6.08	5.66	5.66	5.63
	3.04	2.87	2.87	2.83
	1.52	1.45	1.46	1.41

The adsorption of calcium and magnesium by the three clay minerals under all conditions appears to be exothermic or their maximum intake is observed to be at 20°. This intake appears to occur in multimolecular layers as their adsorption values do not obey Langmuir's equation of adsorption.

References

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214°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = 47^\circ$ (in CHCl_3), m.p. of benzoate derivative = 264°. The compound gave positive Salkowsky reaction², Libermann—Burchard reaction³, red colour with Noller's reagent⁴, reddish violet colour in Brieskorn test⁵, Tischugajen reaction⁶ and yellow colour with tetra nitromethane⁷ Ruzicka. Thus it is identified as Lupeol. Mixed melting point determination with an authentic sample of lupeol also confirmed its identity as lupeol.

The identification of this compound is further supported by spectral data, U. V. (Methanol) $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 200 \text{ m}\mu$ I. R. (KBr) = 3235 (M), 1640 (W), 1490 (W), 1382 (M), 1185 (W), 1105 (W), 1040 (W), 114 (W), 985 (W), 945 (W) cm^{-1} , N.M.R. in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal standard, showed signals at 4.64 and 3.18 τ .

References

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Lupeol from the seed of *Lycopersicon esculentum*

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Chemical Examination of Stem Cuttings of *Pterospermum heyneanum* Wall

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*LYCOSPERSICON esculentum*¹ belongs to the family Solanaceae and is rich in Vitamins A and C.

Experimental

Dried and finely powdered seed of *L. esculentum* on extraction with petroleum ether (40–60°) in a soxhlet extractor and the extract on concentration (150 ml) yielded a greenish white deposit (0.9 gm). The deposit was dissolved in hot methanol and when cooled, a white mass (0.7 gm) was separated, which on crystallisation yielded a white crystalline compound m. p. 213.5°, C = 84.43%, H = 11.62%, molecular weight by semi-micro rast = 399, molecular formula $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = 27^\circ$ (in CHCl_3), m. p. of acetylated derivative

PLANT. Pterospermum heyneanum (N. O. Leguminosae). Uses. medicinal.¹ Previous work. Nil. Present work. Powdered, air dried stem cuttings were extracted with hot ethanol. The viscous mass obtained on concentration under reduced pressure was then extracted successively with petroleum ether, benzene, ether, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol. The petroleum ether extract, on concentration, deposited a yellow solid which on chromatography over neutral alumina, followed by preparative T.L.C. yielded a compound, m.p. 13'–7°, which was identified as β -sitosterol² (m.p. m.m.p. superimposable IR).

The ether extract obtained was concentrated, dried, chromatographed over a column of silica gel. Elution with ethyl acetate, yielded another compound, molecular formula, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6$, m.p. 276–8°. It was